

Spectrophotometric Studies on Palladium(II)-Trifluoroperazine Dihydrochloride Complex

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Trifluoroperazine dihydrochloride forms a stable red coloured complex with palladium(II) instantaneously in the pH range 0.0-3.5. The complex has a maximum absorbance at 480 nm with molar absorptivity $3.92 \times 10^3 \text{ l mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The results of Job's method of continuous variation, molar ratio method and slope ratio method indicate 1:1 composition for the complex which obeys Beer's law in the range of 0.2 to 20 μg of palladium(II) per ml.

TRIFLUOROPERAZINE dihydrochloride. TFP, 10-[3-(4-methyl-1-piperazinyl)propyl]-2-trifluoromethyl phenothiazine dihydrochloride is an important tranquilizing agent which has the following structure :

Palladium chloride was proposed for the identification of TFP¹. The literature survey shows that the red coloured palladium-TFP complex was not investigated for its composition and determination of palladium. This paper describes the results on the composition and other characteristics of the Pd-TFP complex and on the spectrophotometric determination of palladium.

Experimental

Apparatus :

Beckman Model DB Spectrophotometer with matched 1 cm quartz cells was used for absorbance measurements. A pH meter Model LI-10, by Electronic and Industrial Instruments, Hyderabad, with glass and calomel electrodes was used for measuring the pH of the solutions.

Reagents :

Standard palladium(II) solution : A stock solution of palladium(II) was prepared by dissolving palladium(II) chloride (M/s Johnson Matthey Chemicals Ltd., London) in double distilled water and then adding small amounts of hydrochloric acid. It was standardised gravimetrically using dimethylglyoxime².

The working solutions were made by suitable dilution of this standardised stock solution.

Trifluoroperazine dihydrochloride solution. A stock solution of TFP (M/s Smith Kline & French) was prepared by dissolving a known amount of TFP in double distilled water and stored in an amber coloured bottle in a refrigerator.

Diverse ions. Solutions of diverse ions of suitable concentrations were prepared using analytical grade reagents.

Procedure recommended for spectrophotometric determinations. Transfer the sample solution containing 5-500 μg of palladium(II) to a 30 ml beaker. Add 5 ml of 0.1% TFP solution. Adjust the pH of the solution to 1.2 with a pH meter by adding hydrochloric acid-sodium acetate solution. Quantitatively transfer the mixture to a 25 ml volumetric flask. Dilute the solution to the mark with double distilled water. Mix the solution thoroughly and measure the absorbance in a 1 cm cell at 480 nm against a corresponding reagent blank prepared in the same way. Calculate the palladium concentration of the sample solution by means of a calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

Preliminary investigations showed that addition of aqueous solution of TFP to the solution of palladium (II) chloride results in the instantaneous formation of a red coloured complex in a solution of varying pH 0.0-4.5. The method of Vosburgh and Cooper³ was used to find out the number of complexes formed under the experimental conditions of study. Mixtures containing 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 mole ratio of palladium (II) to TFP were prepared keeping the total volume 25 ml and adjusting the pH in the range 0.0 to 3.5 in each case. Absorbance of solutions, at different wavelengths, was measured in each case. Only one sharp maximum was obtained at 480 nm in each case indicating the presence of only one complex. All subsequent studies were performed at 480 nm.

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Absorption spectra. The absorption spectra of the ligand TFP, palladium chloride and the palladium (II)-TFP complex against double distilled water as blank are shown in Fig. 1. The complex exhibits maximum absorbance at 480 nm at which point neither the palladium(II) ion nor TFP absorbs.

Effect of pH time. The effect of pH on the stability of the complex was determined by preparing a series of solutions varying in pH from 0 to 5.5 and the absorbance was found to be maximum and to remain constant between pH 0 and 3.5 over a period of 96 hr. However, the red complex is not formed if the pH of the medium is above 4.5. The order of addition of reactants had no effect on the intensity of the complex colour.

Effect of concentration of reagent and temperature. The concentration of TFP was varied upto 100-fold molar excess, other factors being kept constant. The results of this study indicated that nine fold molar excess of the reagent is required for complete complexation. The optimum amount of the reagent was 5 ml of a 0.1% reagent solution in a final volume of 25 ml.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of (A) TFP, (B) Palladium chloride and (C, D, E, F) Palladium-TFP complex; (C) pH: 0.0-3.5; (D) pH 3.75; (E) pH: 3.85; (F) pH: 4.0
Reference: water; concentration of palladium = 10 µg/ml; concentration of TFP = 0.005M.

The absorbance was independent of the temperature of the colour development over the range 0^o-97^o.

Range for Beer's law and photometric determination. It was found that Beer's law holds good in the range of concentration of palladium from 0.2 to 20 ppm. To evaluate optimum range and analytical accuracy, Ringbom's curve⁴ was drawn by plotting percentage

transmittance as ordinate against log concentration of palladium as abscissa. The range as derived by the maximum slope of the curve was 1 to 18 ppm of palladium.

Molar absorptivity and sensitivity of the complex. A molar absorptivity of 3.92×10^3 l mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ was obtained for the palladium-TFP complex at 480 nm. According to Sandell's expression, the sensitivity of the reaction was 0.027 µg Pd cm⁻². The sensitivity of TFP is more than that of 8-mercaptoquinoline⁵, methylglyoxime^{5,6}, salicylaldoxime^{5,6} and TH⁷ which have been proposed as sensitive spectrophotometric reagents for palladium (II).

Reproducibility. The mean absorbance studied for 10 different samples each containing a final palladium concentration of 10 ppm, has been found to be 0.360 with a standard deviation of 0.002. The accuracy of the determination is ±1.0%.

Effect of diverse ions. In order to assess possible analytical applications of the reaction, the effects of some ions which often accompany palladium were studied. For these studies, different amounts of the ionic species were added to 250 µg palladium (II) solution contained in 25 ml volumetric flasks and the colour was developed exactly as outlined in the standard procedure. The results are listed in Table 1. Alkali and alkaline earth ions caused no interference. Ions showing strong interferences are noble metals, EDTA, Fe³⁺, I⁻ and S₂O₃²⁻.

TABLE I. EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS ON THE DETERMINATION OF PALLADIUM

Ion added	Amount tolerated (ppm) for 250 µg palladium	Ion added	Amount tolerated (ppm) for 250 µg palladium
F ⁻	120	Au ³⁺	0.2
Cl ⁻	1600	Pt ⁴⁺	6.0
Br ⁻	320	Ru ³⁺	2.0
I ⁻	0.2	Os ⁸⁺	32.0
NO ₃ ⁻	2800	Rh ³⁺	8.0
SO ₄ ²⁻	1200	Ir ³⁺	10.0
S ₂ O ₃ ²⁻	0.2	Fe ³⁺	0.1
PO ₄ ³⁻	160	Co ²⁺	100.0
CH ₃ COO ⁻	800	Ni ²⁺	450.0
Citrate	400	Cu ²⁺	1000.0
Oxalate	120	EDTA	2.0

Composition of the complex. The composition of the palladium(II) TFP complex was studied by three different methods at pH ≈ 1.2.

- i) Job's method of continuous variation⁸ using equimolar solutions,
- ii) Mole ratio method⁹,
- iii) Slope ratio method¹⁰.

Job's method of equimolar solutions showed that the stoichiometric ratio of palladium(II) to TFP is 1:1. The molar ratio method and the slope ratio method confirm the 1:1 composition of the complex.

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